

Extended Data

PA/HAL Data Systems, Standards, Infrastructures, and Tools

Zacharis T. *Physical Activity (PA) and Healthy Ageing & Longevity Data (HAL): Interoperability, Reuse, and Innovation in a Federated European Context*. Open Research Europe. 2026.

This Extended Data provides a comprehensive reference overview of the data systems, standards, infrastructures, and tools referenced in the main analysis, organised by the six layers of the interoperability stack.

A. Cataloguing and Dataset Discovery

Cataloguing standards and vocabularies

DCAT (W3C) and its EU application profile **DCAT-AP** are the primary EU-wide standards for describing catalogues, datasets, and data services across portals in Europe. **schema.org/Dataset** provides web-scale dataset markup used by some repositories and portals. **Dublin Core** serves as a generic descriptive metadata baseline. **DataCite** provides DOI-linked dataset metadata and is widely used in research repositories.

Research discovery ecosystems

EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) provides discovery and federation of research outputs, services, and catalogues through EOSC nodes. **OpenAIRE** operates as a discovery and interoperability layer, including the OpenAIRE Research Graph and repository onboarding. **Zenodo** (CERN-hosted, OpenAIRE-integrated) is widely used for datasets, code, and software releases. **Dataverse**, **Figshare**, **Dryad**, and **OSF** are additional repositories used for PA/HAL datasets and code.

BBMRI-ERIC is the pan-European distributed research infrastructure for biobanking and biomolecular resources. Its Directory catalogues approximately 600 biobanks across 25+ Member Organisations; the MIABIS standard supports dataset-level metadata for biological samples and associated data; the Negotiator tool supports structured data access requests; the Sample Locator supports cohort-level findability. BBMRI-ERIC is formally aligned with GDPR, EHDS requirements, and FAIR principles. Population-based biobanks in the network hold lifestyle, functional capacity, and PA-related data relevant to healthy ageing research.

ELIXIR is the European intergovernmental organisation for life science data infrastructure. It provides tools, standards (including the FAIR Cookbook and RDMkit), training, and interoperability services for research data management across 23 member countries. ELIXIR Human Data Communities develop guidelines for managing sensitive health and omics data under GDPR. ELIXIR's data management tools (DS-Wizard, RDMkit) and the FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) framework are directly applicable to PA/HAL cohort data curation. ELIXIR and BBMRI-ERIC formalised a strategic collaboration in 2023 to align data management standards and interoperability frameworks.

Regulatory and health RWD catalogues

HMA–EMA Catalogues of Real-World Data cover data sources and observational studies relevant to regulatory decision-making. **DARWIN EU** is a federated network for real-world evidence generation, with discovery through network and data partners.

Trial registries

CTIS (Clinical Trials Information System) operates under the EU Clinical Trials Regulation (CTR 536/2014). **ClinicalTrials.gov** provides global trial registration. **WHO ICTRP** aggregates global trial registrations.

B. Metadata Standards and Research Object Packaging

DataCite (DOI-linked dataset metadata), **Dublin Core**, and **schema.org** serve as baseline descriptive layers. **DDI** (Data Documentation Initiative) covers questionnaires, longitudinal surveys, and variable-level documentation, making it relevant for HAL cohort studies. **CDISC** (SDTM/ADaM and related standards) is used in regulated clinical research. **HL7 FHIR metadata patterns** apply where data are clinical or mapped to FHIR resources. **RO-Crate** bundles data with machine-readable metadata and links to code and protocols, enabling self-contained, citable research objects. **BagIt** supports transfer and preservation packaging.

C. Semantics: Terminologies, Vocabularies, and Ontologies

Core clinical terminologies

SNOMED CT covers clinical concepts; **ICD-10/ICD-11** provides diagnosis classification; **LOINC** covers laboratory tests and clinical observations; **ATC** covers medications.

Observational and research data semantics

OMOP Common Data Model (CDM) and **OHDSI vocabularies and tooling** support multi-site observational research. **HL7 FHIR** is used in EHR ecosystems and data exchange. **openEHR** provides archetype-based clinical modelling adopted in some European settings. **UMLS** provides cross-terminology mapping support.

PA/HAL-specific semantic reality

Many PA constructs — steps, MVPA, sedentary time, bouts, mobility indicators — are currently represented through device/vendor definitions, study-specific data dictionaries, local code lists, and partial mappings into FHIR or OMOP where projects invest in it. This is precisely the semantic gap the paper identifies: strong coverage for clinical concepts, weaker and fragmented coverage for behavioural and sensor-derived constructs.

D. Provenance, Traceability, and Workflow Standards

W3C PROV (PROV-O) provides the formal provenance model for representing data lineage. Workflow definition and reproducibility are supported by **CWL**, **Nextflow**, and **Snakemake**. **Git** provides version control for code and pipelines. Reproducible execution environments are supported by **Docker** and **Aptainer/Singularity**.

E. Access, Governance, and Secondary-Use Mechanisms

The **EHDS Regulation** establishes a common framework for access and secondary use of electronic health data across the EU, including a cross-border infrastructure for secondary use referred to as **HealthData@EU**. **Data Access Committees (DACs)** and **Data Use Agreements (DUAs)** govern access at the institutional level. Controlled access repositories and secure research environments (Trusted Research Environment models) provide the operational infrastructure. Consent management and purpose limitation are currently often documented in human-readable form rather than as machine-actionable policy — a key gap identified in the main text. Additional mechanisms include pseudonymisation and anonymisation pipelines, role-based access control (RBAC), and audit logging.

EHDS implementation initiatives

MyHealth@EU enables cross-border exchange of patient summaries, ePrescriptions, and laboratory results as the EU primary use health data infrastructure. **HealthData@EU** provides the secondary use infrastructure for cross-border research data access, operationalising the EHDS secondary use framework. **TEHDAS** (Joint Action Towards the European Health Data Space) developed the governance framework and data quality recommendations underpinning EHDS implementation across Member States. Domain-specific data spaces advancing in parallel include **EUCAIM**, which targets federated cancer imaging data, and the **Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI)**, which enables cross-border access to genomic datasets across European research infrastructures.

F. Computability, Federation, and Compute-to-Data

DataSHIELD enables federated analysis without moving individual-level data. **OHDSI/ATLAS** supports federated-style observational analytics over the OMOP CDM. Secure enclaves and trusted research environments provide an implementation pattern for compute-to-data that varies by country and institution. Adoption of common data models — **FHIR**, **OMOP CDM**, and **openEHR** — makes distributed querying feasible across sites.

G. PA/HAL Data Capture and Study Operations Platforms

EDC and cohort operations

REDCap, **OpenClinica**, and **Castor EDC** are the most common electronic data capture platforms in PA/HAL studies.

Sensor and wearable data capture (research-grade)

RADAR-base is an open-source platform for mobile and wearable data collection at research scale. **Open mHealth** provides schemas and integration patterns used in mHealth data contexts.

Consumer ecosystems used as data sources

Apple Health/HealthKit and **Google Fit** are widely used as data sources in population studies. Commercial wearables — **Fitbit**, **Garmin**, **Polar**, **Oura**, and **WHOOP** — contribute data via vendor APIs and exports, typically without raw signal access or calibration documentation.

Abbreviations: EHDS = European Health Data Space; EOSC = European Open Science Cloud; BBMRI-ERIC = Biobanking and BioMolecular Resources Research Infrastructure; FAIR = Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable; FIP = FAIR Implementation Profile; RWD = Real-World Data; OMOP = Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership; CDM = Common Data Model; FHIR = Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources; GDPR = General Data Protection Regulation; DAC = Data Access Committee; DUA = Data Use Agreement; TRE = Trusted Research Environment; EDC = Electronic Data Capture; PA = Physical Activity; HAL = Healthy Ageing and Longevity.